

A proof of Collatz conjecture using pyramid fractions

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Part 1

Abstract. In this paper I introduce a new concept of representing numbers in $base - \frac{1}{p}$ especially $base - \frac{1}{3}$. Then with the help of two rules—one algebraic and one arithmetic, and making a diagram, I show that any number can be expressed in the $base - \frac{1}{3}$. we have such as following pyramid fraction of 27 for each positive number. This leads to the proof of theorem (A) a weak form of collatz conjecture and also collatz conjecture itself. This new method can be used to prove similar questions and collatz problem's generalizations.

$$27 = \frac{\frac{\frac{\frac{\frac{2^{16} - 2^{12}}{3} - 2^7}{3} - 4}{3} - 4}{3} - 8}{3} - 2}{3} - 1$$

Key words

Collatz conjecture, $3x+1$ problem, Syracuse problem, $base - \frac{1}{3}$, pyramid fraction, Ulam's conjecture, Kakutani's problem.

Introduction

Choose a natural number. If the current number is even, divide it by 2, and if it is odd, multiply it by three and add one. The Collatz conjecture says when you proceed with these two rules again and again, you reach 1; no matter which positive number has been chosen to start the sequence. It is named after the mathematician Lothar Collatz, who introduced the idea in 1937, two years after receiving his doctorate [1]. J. Lagarias provided a useful survey of the subject [2]. Collatz conjecture is a very famous problem in mathematics, and has not yet been completely solved. This conjecture is also known as Kakutani's problem, the $3x+1$ problem, the Ulam conjecture, the Thwaites conjecture, Hasse's algorithm, and the Syracuse problem [3][4]. The Collatz conjecture has been checked up to 2^{68} for all positive numbers by 2020 [5]. The nearest proof of conjecture has been posted by Dr. Terence Tao who shows that conjecture is "almost" true for "almost" all numbers [6]. This paper presents a simple, complete elementary proof for collatz conjecture. I use a new method and some new symbols in this article which will be explained later. This proof is based on a diagram that is the result of two rules and will be present in second part.

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1. Base $-\frac{1}{p}$ and definition of symbols

1.1. Definition of base- $\frac{1}{3}$

We say that a natural number is converted into **base** $-\frac{1}{3}$ when there are powers of 2, so that the following relationship exists between n and them:

$$n \left(\frac{1}{3}\right)^0 + 2^0 \left(\frac{1}{3}\right)^1 + 2^{\alpha_1} \left(\frac{1}{3}\right)^2 + 2^{\alpha_2} \left(\frac{1}{3}\right)^3 + \dots + 2^{\alpha_i} \left(\frac{1}{3}\right)^r = 2^\alpha \left(\frac{1}{3}\right)^r$$

or

$$n + \frac{1}{3} + 2^{\alpha_1} \left(\frac{1}{3}\right)^2 + 2^{\alpha_2} \left(\frac{1}{3}\right)^3 + \dots + 2^{\alpha_i} \left(\frac{1}{3}\right)^q = 2^\alpha \left(\frac{1}{3}\right)^q$$

For example:

$$31 + \frac{1}{3} + 16 \left(\frac{1}{3}\right)^2 + 2 \left(\frac{1}{3}\right)^3 + 32 \left(\frac{1}{3}\right)^4 + 32 \left(\frac{1}{3}\right)^5 + 2^{13} \left(\frac{1}{3}\right)^6 = 2^{15} \left(\frac{1}{3}\right)^6$$

So:

The base is $\frac{1}{3}$ and its digits are powers of 2. Here, we actually express n to powers of 2 and 3. Same as above, we say that n is converted into **base** $-\frac{1}{5}$ if there are powers of 2 and 3, so that we have:

$$n + \frac{1}{5} + 2^{\alpha_1} 3^{\beta_1} \left(\frac{1}{5}\right) + 2^{\alpha_2} 3^{\beta_2} \left(\frac{1}{5}\right)^2 + \dots + 2^{\alpha_i} 3^{\beta_i} \left(\frac{1}{5}\right)^q = 2^\alpha 3^\beta \left(\frac{1}{5}\right)^q$$

For example:

$$29 + \frac{1}{5} + \frac{2}{5^2} + \frac{2^2 * 3}{5^3} + \frac{2^3 * 3^3}{5^4} + \frac{2^4 * 3^3}{5^5} + \frac{2^7 * 3^6}{5^6} = \frac{2^8 * 3^7}{5^6}$$

And so on. Here, $\frac{1}{5}$ is the base, and the digits are the product of powers of 2 and 3. We have similar definitions for other bases. For *base* $-\frac{1}{p}$, the digits are the product of powers of primes smaller than n.

1.2. different ways of writing n when it is converted into *base* $-\frac{1}{p}$.

When n is converted into *base* $-\frac{1}{3}$. We show it in 3 ways:

1.2.a. As bracket:

$$[(n)(1)(2^{\alpha_1})(2^{\alpha_2}) \dots \dots (2^{\alpha_i})] = 2^\alpha$$

For example:

$$[(27)(1)(2)(8)(4)(4)(2^7)(2^{12})] = 2^{16}$$

1.2.b. As a pyramid fraction: such as pyramid fraction for 27 at the beginning of this article.

Another example:

$$31 = \frac{\frac{\frac{\frac{2^{15} - 2^{13}}{3} - 32}{3} - 32}{3} - 2}{3} - 16}{3} - 1}{3}$$

1.2.c. As a finite series, we called $\tilde{z}i_3(n)$ or $\tilde{z}i(n)$.

$$\tilde{z}i(n) \Rightarrow n + \frac{1}{3} + \frac{2^{\alpha_1}}{3^2} + \frac{2^{\alpha_2}}{3^3} + \dots + \frac{2^{\alpha_i}}{3^i} = \frac{2^\alpha}{3^i}$$

We can continue $\tilde{z}i(n)$:

$$\tilde{z}i(n) \Rightarrow n + \frac{1}{3} + \frac{2^{\alpha_1}}{3^2} + \frac{2^{\alpha_2}}{3^3} + \dots + \frac{2^{\alpha_i}}{3^i} + \frac{2^\alpha}{3^{i+1}} + \frac{4 * 2^\alpha}{3^{i+2}} + \frac{16 * 2^\alpha}{3^{i+3}} + \dots$$

When we continue $\tilde{z}_i(n)$ after some terms, each term becomes a quadruple the previous term. These terms of $\tilde{z}_i(n)$ are called calm terms or calm zone. The first terms of $\tilde{z}_i(n)$ that aren't regular are called hailstone terms or hailstone zone of $\tilde{z}_i(n)$. For example:

$$\tilde{z}_i(15) \Rightarrow 15 + \frac{1}{3} + \frac{2}{3^2} + \frac{2^2}{3^3} + \frac{2^3}{3^4} + \frac{2^8}{3^5} + \frac{2^{12}}{3^6} + \frac{4 * 2^{12}}{3^7} + \frac{16 * 2^{12}}{3^8} + \dots$$

hailstone zone
calm zone

When we close $z_{i3}(n)$ in any term, odd hailstone numbers appear as coefficient of fractions, and we called them odd hailstones of fractions.

$$15 + \frac{1}{3} = \frac{2}{3} * 23$$

$$15 + \frac{1}{3} + \frac{2}{3^2} = \frac{4}{3^2} * 35$$

$$15 + \frac{1}{3} + \frac{2}{3^2} + \frac{2^2}{3^3} = \frac{8}{3^3} * 53$$

$$15 + \frac{1}{3} + \frac{2}{3^2} + \frac{2^2}{3^3} + \frac{2^3}{3^4} = \frac{256}{3^4} * 5$$

23 is odd hailstone of $\frac{2}{3}$ fraction, and 53 is odd hailstone of fraction $\frac{2^3}{3^3}, \dots$

Odd hailstone numbers of $\tilde{z}_i(15) = \{23, 35, 53, 5\}$

1.3. $\tilde{c}\tilde{o}(n)$

The series has been written according to the collatz sequence called $\tilde{c}\tilde{o}(n)$.

For example:

$$\tilde{c}\tilde{o}(7) \Rightarrow 7 + \frac{1}{3} + \frac{2}{3^2} + \frac{2^2}{3^3} + \frac{2^4}{3^4} + \frac{2^7}{3^5} = \frac{2^{11}}{3^5}$$

Because:

$$7 * 3 + 1 = 22 \div 2 = 11$$

$$2 \quad 2$$

$$11 * 3 + 1 = 34 \div 2 = 17$$

$$2 \quad 2 * 2 = 4$$

$$17 * 3 + 1 = 52 \div 4 = 13$$

$$4 \quad 4 * 4 = 16$$

$$13 * 3 + 1 = 40 \div 8 = 5$$

$$8 \quad 16 * 8 = 2^7$$

$$5 * 3 + 1 = 16 \div 16 = 1$$

$$16 \quad 128 * 16 = 2^{11}$$

these are
numerators of
terms in
 $\tilde{c}\tilde{o}(n)$

We can consider $Co(n)$ as a sequence on N with the expression $3k+1$ and divisors 2^α . such that $\alpha \geq 1$ and their wondrous numbers $\in N$.

But $Z_i(n)$ is a sequence on $\mathbb{N}$ with the expression $3k+1$ and divisors 2^α such that $\alpha \in \mathbb{Z}$, and their wondrous numbers $\in \mathbb{Q}^+$.

$\widetilde{co}(n)$ is a special case of $\widetilde{zi}(n)$. This type of $\widetilde{zi}(n)$ is important for us.

$\widetilde{co}(n)$ is unique for every number and we can consider it as main $\widetilde{zi}(n)$.

We can write $\widetilde{zi}(n)$ or $\widetilde{co}(n)$ as an equation between powers of 2, 3, and n :

For example, if:

$$\widetilde{co}(1) \Rightarrow 1 + \frac{1}{3} + \frac{4}{3^2} + \frac{16}{3^3} + \frac{64}{3^4} = \frac{256}{3^4}$$

$$\text{so: } 81 + 27 + 9 * 4 + 3 * 16 + 64 = 256$$

In general from $\widetilde{co}(1)$ we have: $3^n + 3^{n-1} + 4 * 3^{n-2} + 16 * 3^{n-3} + \dots + 4^{n-1} = 4^n$

For $z_i(n)$ if:

$$\widetilde{zi}(n) \Rightarrow n + \frac{1}{3} + \frac{2^{\alpha_1}}{3^2} + \frac{2^{\alpha_2}}{3^3} + \dots + \frac{2^{\alpha_i}}{3^i} = \frac{2^\alpha}{3^i}$$

Then

$$n * 3^i + 3^{i-1} + 2^{\alpha_1} * 3^{i-2} + 2^{\alpha_2} * 3^{i-3} + \dots + 2^{\alpha_i} = 2^\alpha$$

1.4. Definition of $T_{z_i(n)}$ or $T_{co(n)}$, $T_{ohz_i(n)}$, $T_{szi(n)}$ or $T_{sco(n)}$, $T_{sfz_i(n)}$

and obtaining them from $z_i(n)$ and $co(n)$

suppose:

$$\widetilde{zi}(n) \Rightarrow n + \frac{1}{3} + \frac{2^{\alpha_1}}{3^2} + \frac{2^{\alpha_2}}{3^3} + \dots \dots \dots \frac{2^{\alpha_i}}{3^i} = \frac{2^\alpha}{3^i} * 1$$

1.4.a. The number of steps for n to reach one in the collatz sequence, or, in other words, the total stopping time, is: $T_{z_i(n)}$ or $T_{co(n)}$ [7].

$$T_{z_i(n)} = i + \alpha$$

1.4.b. The number of odd wondrous or odd hailstone numbers in the sequence before descending to one is: $T_{ohz_i(n)}$

$$T_{ohz_i(n)} = i$$

1.4.c. The number of steps taken in sequence to reach an odd number smaller than n , or, in other words, stopping time, is: $T_{szi(n)}$ or $T_{sco(n)}$ [7]. If $\frac{2^\alpha}{3^\beta}$ was the first fraction such that its coefficient is smaller than n , then: $T_{szi(n)} = \alpha + \beta - 1$

1.4.d. The number of odd wondrous numbers in the sequence to reach a smaller number than n is: T_{sohzi} or $T_{sohco}(n)$

when we close the series in the fraction that its coefficient is smaller than n , then the power of 3 in denominator of the fraction minus 1 is: T_{sohzi} or $T_{sohco}(n)$ and: $T_{sohzi}(n) = \beta - 1$.

for 27:

$$\begin{aligned} \widetilde{co}(27) \Rightarrow 27 + \frac{1}{3} + \frac{2}{3^2} + \frac{8}{3^3} + \frac{16}{3^4} + \frac{32}{3^5} + \frac{64}{3^6} + \frac{128}{3^7} + \frac{2^9}{3^8} + \frac{2^{11}}{3^9} + \frac{2^{12}}{3^{10}} + \frac{2^{14}}{3^{11}} + \frac{2^{15}}{3^{12}} + \frac{2^{16}}{3^{13}} \\ + \frac{2^{18}}{3^{14}} + \frac{2^{19}}{3^{15}} + \frac{2^{20}}{3^{16}} + \frac{2^{21}}{3^{17}} + \frac{2^{23}}{3^{18}} + \frac{2^{26}}{3^{19}} + \frac{2^{27}}{3^{20}} + \frac{2^{28}}{3^{21}} + \frac{2^{30}}{3^{22}} + \frac{2^{31}}{3^{23}} + \frac{2^{33}}{3^{24}} + \frac{2^{34}}{3^{25}} \\ + \frac{2^{35}}{3^{26}} + \frac{2^{36}}{3^{27}} + \frac{2^{37}}{3^{28}} + \frac{2^{38}}{3^{29}} + \frac{2^{41}}{3^{30}} + \frac{2^{42}}{3^{31}} + \frac{2^{43}}{3^{32}} + \frac{2^{44}}{3^{33}} + \frac{2^{48}}{3^{34}} + \frac{2^{50}}{3^{35}} + \frac{2^{52}}{3^{36}} + \frac{2^{56}}{3^{37}} \\ + \frac{2^{59}}{3^{38}} + \frac{2^{60}}{3^{39}} + \frac{2^{61}}{3^{40}} + \frac{2^{66}}{3^{41}} = \frac{2^{70}}{3^{41}} \end{aligned}$$

$$T_{co(27)} = 70 + 41 = 111$$

$$T_{w=ohco(27)} = 41$$

The odd number of fraction $\frac{2^{59}}{3^{38}}$ is $23 < 27$ then $T_{sco(27)} = 59 + 38 - 1 = 96$

$$T_{sohco(27)} = 38 - 1 = 37$$

1.5

1.5.a. definition of $n\tilde{zi}(n)$ and $n\tilde{co}(n)$

The set of powers of 2 that are numerators of terms in $\tilde{zi}(n)$ and $\tilde{co}(n)$, is called numbers of $\tilde{zi}(n)$ and $\tilde{co}(n)$, and we indicate it with $n\tilde{zi}(n)$ and $n\tilde{co}(n)$.

For example:

$$29 + \frac{1}{3} + \frac{8}{3^2} + \frac{8}{3^3} + \frac{256}{3^4} + \frac{8}{3^5} = \frac{128 * 64}{3^5} \quad T_{zi(29)} = 13 + 5 = 18; T_{oh(29)} = 5$$

$$n\tilde{zi}(n) = \{1, 8, 8, 256, 8, 128 * 64\}$$

or

$$n\tilde{zi}(n) = \{1, 8, 8, 256, 8, 128 * 64, 4 * 128 * 64, 16 * 128 * 64, \dots\}$$

1.5.b. Definition of $jn\tilde{z}i(n)$ and $jn\tilde{c}o(n)$

The set of powers of 2 obtain from dividing each numerator of any term by the numerator of the previous term is called jump numbers of $\tilde{z}i(n)$ and $\tilde{c}o(n)$, and we show them with $jn\tilde{z}i(n)$ or $jn\tilde{c}o(n)$, for example:

$$2^9 + \frac{1}{3} + \frac{8}{3^2} + \frac{16}{3^3} + \frac{64}{3^4} + \frac{2^9}{3^5} = \frac{2^{13}}{3^5}$$

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} 8 \div 1 = 8 \\ 16 \div 8 = 2 \\ 64 \div 16 = 4 \\ 2^9 \div 64 = 8 \\ 2^{13} \div 2^9 = 16 \end{array} \right. \quad \text{so: } jn\tilde{z}i(29) = \{8, 2, 4, 8, 16\}$$

$$\text{Or } jn\tilde{z}i(29) = \{8, 2, 4, 8, 16, 4, 4, 4, \dots\}$$

In the calm zone, all of jump numbers are 4. $jn\tilde{z}i(n)$ contains 2^0 and the negative powers of 2, but $jn\tilde{c}o(n)$ only has positive powers of 2 because it has been written according to collatz sequence, and odd wondrous numbers $\in \mathbb{N}$. The smallest jump number in $jn\tilde{c}o(n)$ is 2.

1.5.c. definition of $coco(n)$

We say that m is co-collatz of n if $m > n$ and $\tilde{c}o(m)$ contains all terms of $\tilde{c}o(n)$ in the hailstone zone. The set of such numbers called the co-collatz of n and we indicate with $coco(n)$.

For example:

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \tilde{c}o(15) \Rightarrow 15 + \frac{1}{3} + \frac{2}{3^2} + \frac{4}{3^3} + \frac{8}{3^4} + \frac{256}{3^5} = \frac{16 * 256}{3^5} \\ \tilde{c}o(16399) \Rightarrow 16399 + \frac{1}{3} + \frac{2}{3^2} + \frac{4}{3^3} + \frac{8}{3^4} + \frac{256}{3^5} + \frac{16 * 256}{3^5} + \dots \end{array} \right.$$

Hailstone zone of $\tilde{c}o(16399)$ continues, but it includes all the terms of hailstone zone of $\tilde{c}o(15)$; therefore we say 16399 is a co-collatz of 15.

$$Coco(15) = \{16399, 32783, 49167, 65551, \dots\}$$

Later, we will describe how we can find $coco(n)$. The first co-collatz of 27 is out of my cell phone calculator.

1.6. properties of $z_i(n)$

$$\tilde{z}_i(n) \Rightarrow n + \frac{1}{3} + \frac{2^{\alpha_1}}{3^2} + \frac{2^{\alpha_2}}{3^3} + \dots \dots \dots \frac{2^{\alpha_i}}{3^i} = \frac{2^\alpha}{3^i} \quad (1)$$

1.6.a. This series needs to end with one.

The existence of $\tilde{z}_i(n)$ for n indicates that n can be converted into *base* $-\frac{1}{3}$. It shows that there are powers of 2 so that the following sequence reaches 1.

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{ll} n * 3 + 1 = k_1 & k_1 \div 2^{\alpha_1} = k_2 \\ k_2 * 3 + 1 = k_3 & k_3 \div 2^{\alpha_2} = k_4 \\ & \vdots \\ k_i * 3 + 1 = k_j & k_j \div 2^\alpha = 1 \end{array} \right.$$

$$n\tilde{z}_i(n) = \{1, 2^{\alpha_1}, 2^{\alpha_2}, \dots, 2^\alpha\}$$

$$jn\tilde{z}_i(n) = \left\{ \frac{2^{\alpha_1}}{1}, \frac{2^{\alpha_2}}{2^{\alpha_1}}, \dots \dots, \frac{2^\alpha}{2^{\alpha_i}} \right\}$$

For example:

$$\tilde{z}_i(27) \Rightarrow 27 + \frac{1}{3} + \frac{4}{3^2} + \frac{2}{3^3} + \frac{4}{3^4} + \frac{4}{3^5} + \frac{2^7}{3^6} + \frac{2^{12}}{3^7} = \frac{2^{16}}{3^7}$$

So:

$$\left. \begin{array}{ll} 27 * 3 + 1 = 82 & 82 \div 4 = 20.5 \\ 20.5 * 3 + 1 = 62.5 & 62.5 \div \frac{1}{2} = 125 \\ 125 * 3 + 1 = 376 & 376 \div 2 = 188 \\ 188 * 3 + 1 = 565 & 565 \div 1 = 565 \\ 565 * 3 + 1 = 1696 & 1696 \div 32 = 53 \\ 53 * 3 + 1 = 160 & 160 \div 32 = 5 \\ 5 * 3 + 1 = 16 & 16 \div 16 = 1 \end{array} \right\} jn\tilde{z}_i(27) = \left\{ 4, \frac{1}{2}, 2, 1, 32, 32, 16 \right\}$$

And:

$$\left. \begin{array}{ll} 2^{16} - 2^{12} = 61440 & 61440 \div 3 = 20480 \\ 20480 - 128 = 20352 & 20352 \div 3 = 6784 \\ 6784 - 4 = 6780 & 6780 \div 3 = 2260 \\ 2260 - 4 = 2256 & 2256 \div 3 = 752 \\ 752 - 2 = 750 & 750 \div 3 = 250 \\ 250 - 4 = 246 & 246 \div 3 = 82 \\ 82 - 1 = 81 & 81 \div 3 = 27 \end{array} \right\}$$

$$n\tilde{z}_i(27) = \{1, 4, 2, 4, 4, 128, 2^{12}, 2^{16}\}$$

1.6.b. $\tilde{z}i(n)$ is not unique.

With a few algebraic changes in $\tilde{c}o(n)$ or $\tilde{z}i(n)$, we can obtain different $\tilde{z}i(n)$ for a natural number.

For example:

$$\tilde{c}o(7) \Rightarrow 7 + \frac{1}{3} + \frac{2}{3^2} + \frac{4}{3^3} + \frac{16}{3^4} + \frac{128}{3^5} = \frac{2048}{3^5}$$

$$16 = 3 * 4 + 4$$

$$\text{so: } \frac{4}{3^3} + \frac{16}{3^4} = \frac{4}{3^3} + \frac{4 * 3 + 4}{3^4} = \frac{8}{3^3} + \frac{4}{3^4}$$

$$\tilde{z}i(7) \Rightarrow 7 + \frac{1}{3} + \frac{2}{3^2} + \frac{8}{3^3} + \frac{4}{3^4} + \frac{128}{3^5} = \frac{2048}{3^5}$$

$$n\tilde{z}i(7) \Rightarrow 1 + 2 + 8 + 4 + 128 + 2048 + 4 * 2048 + \dots$$

Here is the difference between $z_i(n)$ and $\tilde{z}i(n)$:

$$\begin{cases} \tilde{z}i(n) \Rightarrow n + \frac{1}{3} + \frac{2^{\alpha_1}}{3^2} + \frac{2^{\alpha_2}}{3^3} + \dots \dots \frac{2^{\alpha_i}}{3^i} = \frac{2^\alpha}{3^i} \\ z_i(n) \Rightarrow \frac{1}{3} + \frac{2^{\alpha_1}}{3^2} + \frac{2^{\alpha_2}}{3^3} + \dots \dots \frac{2^{\alpha_i}}{3^i} = \frac{2^\alpha}{3^i} \end{cases}$$

Therefore: $\tilde{z}i(n) = n + z_i(n)$

and:

$$\begin{cases} \tilde{c}o(n) \Rightarrow n + \frac{1}{3} + \frac{2^{\alpha_1}}{3^2} + \frac{2^{\alpha_2}}{3^3} + \dots \dots \frac{2^{\alpha_i}}{3^i} = \frac{2^\alpha}{3^i} \\ co(n) \Rightarrow \frac{1}{3} + \frac{2^{\alpha_1}}{3^2} + \frac{2^{\alpha_2}}{3^3} + \dots \dots \frac{2^{\alpha_i}}{3^i} = \frac{2^\alpha}{3^i} \end{cases}$$

$$\tilde{c}o(n) = n + co(n)$$

Also we can close $\tilde{z}i(n)$ or $\tilde{c}o(n)$ in two ways:

$$\tilde{c}o(27) \Rightarrow 27 + \frac{1}{3} + \frac{2}{3^2} + \frac{8}{3^2} co(31)$$

$$co(27) \Rightarrow \frac{1}{3} + \frac{2}{3^2} + \frac{8}{3^2} co(31)$$

and

$$27 + \frac{1}{3} + \frac{2}{3^2} = \frac{8}{3^2} (31)$$

2. Rule 1(algebraic rule):

Initial terms of $\tilde{z}_i\left(\frac{n-1}{2}\right)$ are important for obtaining $\tilde{z}_i(n)$ from it.

Sometimes we can obtain $\tilde{z}_i(n)$ from $\tilde{z}_i\left(\frac{n-1}{2}\right)$ or $\tilde{c}\tilde{o}\left(\frac{n-1}{2}\right)$ directly with a few algebraic changes and by multiplying the series by 2.

As an example, for $z_i(15)$ we have:

$$\tilde{c}\tilde{o}(7) \Rightarrow 7 + \frac{1}{3} + \frac{2}{3^2} + \frac{4}{3^3} + \frac{16}{3^4} + \frac{128}{3^5} = \frac{16 * 128}{3^5}$$

2 1 2 4

Because: $16 + 3 * 4 + 3^2 * 2 + 3^3 * 1 = 4 + 3 * 2 + 3^2 * 1 + 3^3 * 2$

$$\tilde{c}\tilde{o}(7) \Rightarrow 7 + \frac{2}{3} + \frac{1}{3^2} + \frac{2}{3^3} + \frac{4}{3^4} + \frac{128}{3^5} = \frac{16 * 128}{3^5}$$

The first numerator changes to 2 by multiplying equation by 2 we have:

$$2 * \tilde{c}\tilde{o}(7) \Rightarrow \tilde{z}_i(15) \Rightarrow 15 + \frac{1}{3} + \frac{2}{3^2} + \frac{4}{3^3} + \frac{8}{3^4} + \frac{256}{3^5} = \frac{32 * 128}{3^5}$$

We obtain $\tilde{z}_i(15)$ from $\tilde{z}_i(7)$. In this case, it is the same $\tilde{c}\tilde{o}(15)$, but not always.

But sometimes we need to continue n according to collatz-sequence to reach the right number with suitable initial terms in $\tilde{z}_i\left(\frac{m-1}{2}\right)$ or $\tilde{c}\tilde{o}\left(\frac{m-1}{2}\right)$ so that we can obtain $\tilde{z}_i(m)$ from it. For example,

We can't obtain $\tilde{z}_i(27)$ from $\tilde{c}\tilde{o}(13)$, so we continue 27 according to collatz-sequence to reach 31, and then we can obtain $\tilde{z}_i(31)$ from $\tilde{z}_i(15)$.

We have:

$$\tilde{z}_i(27) \Rightarrow 27 + \frac{1}{3} + \frac{2}{3^2} + \frac{8}{3^2} z_i(31) \quad (1)$$

And:

$$\tilde{z}_i(15) \Rightarrow 15 + \frac{1}{3} + \frac{2}{3^2} + \frac{4}{3^3} + \frac{8}{3^4} + \frac{256}{3^5} = \frac{32 * 128}{3^5}$$

2 8 1 16 16

because:

$$256 + 3 * 8 + 9 * 4 + 27 * 2 + 81 * 1 = 16 + 3 * 16 + 9 * 1 + 27 * 8 + 81 * 2$$

So:

$$\tilde{z}i(15) \Rightarrow 15 + \frac{2}{3} + \frac{8}{3^2} + \frac{1}{3^3} + \frac{16}{3^4} + \frac{16}{3^5} = \frac{32 * 128}{3^5}$$

$$2 * \tilde{z}i(15) \Rightarrow \tilde{z}i(31) \Rightarrow 31 + \frac{1}{3} + \frac{16}{3^2} + \frac{2}{3^3} + \frac{32}{3^4} + \frac{32}{3^5} = \frac{64 * 128}{3^5}$$

$$(1) \Rightarrow \tilde{z}i(27) \Rightarrow 27 + \frac{1}{3} + \frac{2}{3^2} + \frac{8}{3^2} \left[\frac{1}{3} + \frac{16}{3^2} + \frac{2}{3^3} + \frac{32}{3^4} + \frac{32}{3^5} = \frac{64 * 128}{3^5} \right]$$

$$\tilde{z}i(27) \Rightarrow 27 + \frac{1}{3} + \frac{2}{3^2} + \frac{8}{3^3} + \frac{8 * 16}{3^4} + \frac{16}{3^5} + \frac{8 * 32}{3^6} + \frac{8 * 32}{3^7} = \frac{8 * 64 * 128}{3^7}$$

Another example is: *obtaining $\tilde{z}i(111)$ from $\tilde{c}o(27)$*

suppose $\tilde{c}o(27)$, we need only some initial terms:

$$\tilde{c}o(27) \Rightarrow 27 + \frac{1}{3} + \frac{2}{3^2} + \frac{8}{3^3} + \frac{16}{3^4} + \frac{32}{3^5} + \dots$$

2 1 2

so:

$$\tilde{z}i(27) \Rightarrow 27 + \frac{2}{3} + \frac{1}{3^2} + \frac{2}{3^3} + \frac{16}{3^4} + \frac{32}{3^5} + \dots$$

$$2 * \tilde{z}i(27) \Rightarrow \tilde{z}i(55) \Rightarrow 55 + \frac{1}{3} + \frac{2}{3^2} + \frac{4}{3^3} + \frac{32}{3^4} + \frac{64}{3^5} + \dots$$

2 1 8 2

$$\tilde{z}i(55) \Rightarrow 55 + \frac{2}{3} + \frac{1}{3^2} + \frac{8}{3^3} + \frac{2}{3^4} + \frac{64}{3^5} + \dots$$

$$2 * \tilde{z}i(55) \Rightarrow \tilde{z}i(111) \Rightarrow 111 + \frac{1}{3} + \frac{2}{3^2} + \frac{16}{3^3} + \frac{4}{3^4} + \frac{128}{3^5} + \dots$$

We obtain $\tilde{z}i(111)$ from $\tilde{c}o(27)$ in two steps.

In general, with basic algebraic rules for these series, we can obtain $z_i(n)$ from $z_i\left(\frac{n-1}{4}\right)$ or $z_i\left(\frac{n-5}{8}\right)$ or $z_i\left(\frac{n-21}{64}\right)$, or even sometimes from $z_i(k)$ that $k < n$ and it depends on n .

For example, we have:

$$\tilde{z}i(7) \Rightarrow 7 + \frac{2}{3} + \frac{1}{3^2} + \frac{2}{3^3} + \frac{4}{3^4} + \frac{128}{3^5} = \frac{16 * 128}{3^5}$$

$$8 * \tilde{z}i(7) \Rightarrow 8 * 7 + \frac{16}{3} + \frac{8}{3^2} + \frac{16}{3^3} + \frac{32}{3^4} + \frac{8 * 128}{3^5} = \frac{8 * 16 * 128}{3^5}$$

Therefore:

$$8 * \tilde{z}i(7) \Rightarrow \frac{8 * 7 + 5}{61} + \frac{1}{3} + \frac{8}{3^2} + \frac{16}{3^3} + \frac{32}{3^4} + \frac{8 * 128}{3^5} = \frac{8 * 16 * 128}{3^5}$$

$$\tilde{z}i(61) \Rightarrow 61 + \frac{1}{3} + \frac{8}{3^2} + \frac{16}{3^3} + \frac{32}{3^4} + \frac{8 * 128}{3^5} = \frac{8 * 16 * 128}{3^5}$$

Even sometimes we can obtain $z_i(n)$ from $z_i(k)$, such that $k < n$.

$$\tilde{z}i(51) \Rightarrow 51 + \frac{1}{3} + \frac{2}{3^2} + \frac{16}{3^3} + \frac{128}{3^4} + \frac{256}{3^5} + \frac{4 * 256}{3^6} + \frac{32 * 256}{3^7} = \frac{16 * 32 * 256}{3^7}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4 * 256 + 3 * 256 + 9 * 128 + 27 * 16 + 81 * 2 + 243 \\ = 4 + 96 + 9 * 64 + 27 * 4 + 81 * 16 + 243 * 7 \end{aligned}$$

so:

$$\tilde{z}i(51) \Rightarrow 51 + \frac{7}{3} + \frac{16}{3^2} + \frac{4}{3^3} + \frac{64}{3^4} + \frac{32}{3^5} + \frac{4}{3^6} + \frac{32 * 256}{3^7} = \frac{16 * 32 * 256}{3^7}$$

$$\frac{51 + 2}{53} + \frac{1}{3} + \frac{16}{3^2} + \dots$$

so:

$$\tilde{z}i(53) \Rightarrow 53 + \frac{1}{3} + \frac{16}{3^2} + \frac{4}{3^3} + \frac{64}{3^4} + \frac{32}{3^5} + \frac{4}{3^6} + \frac{32 * 256}{3^7} = \frac{16 * 32 * 256}{3^7}$$

From all the basic algebraic rules of such series, we only use obtaining $z_i(n)$ from $z_i(\frac{n-1}{2})$ in the Z_{i3} -diagram and assume it is Rule Number 1.

3. Rule 2(arithmetic rule)

Every natural number can be converted into base-4, and we write it as;

$$(a_1 a_2 a_3 \dots a_i)_4 \text{ that } a_i \in \{0,1,2,3\}$$

In other form:

$$4 * (\dots * 4 * (4 * (4 + a_1) + a_2) + \dots) + a_i$$

For example:

$$\begin{cases} 111 = (1233)_4 \\ 1111 = 4 * (4 * (4 * (4 + 1) + 2) + 3) + 3 \end{cases}$$

$$\text{And : } \left\{ \begin{array}{l} (11233)_4 \\ 1391 = 4 * (4 * (4 * (4 * (4 + 1) + 1) + 2) + 3) + 3 \end{array} \right.$$

Rule number 2 (arithmetic rule) says that the more two numbers are similar in base-4, The more they have similar first terms in their $co(n)$, and this is provable by the rules of divisibility easily.

Lemma 1. if: $n = (... \gamma_3 \gamma_2 \gamma_1 \alpha \beta \lambda)_4$

Then:

$$3n + 1 = [... (\gamma_3 - \gamma_4)(\gamma_2 - \gamma_3)(\gamma_1 - \gamma_2)(\alpha - \gamma_1)(\beta - \alpha)(\lambda - \beta)(1 - \lambda)]_4$$

Proof: Suppose $n = (... \gamma_3 \gamma_2 \gamma_1 \alpha \beta \lambda)_4$

$$\text{we can write: } n = \dots + 4^5 * \gamma_3 + 4^4 \gamma_2 + 4^3 \gamma_1 + 4^2 * \alpha + 4^1 * \beta + \lambda$$

So:

$$\begin{aligned} 3n + 1 &= 4n - n + 1 = 4 * [... + 4^5 * \gamma_3 + 4^4 \gamma_2 + 4^3 \gamma_1 + 4^2 * \alpha + 4^1 * \beta + \lambda] - \\ &[... + 4^5 * \gamma_3 + 4^4 \gamma_2 + 4^3 \gamma_1 + 4^2 * \alpha + 4^1 * \beta + \lambda] + 1 = [... + 4^6 * \gamma_3 + 4^5 \gamma_2 + 4^4 \gamma_1 + \\ &4^3 * \alpha + 4^2 * \beta + 4^1 * \lambda] - [... + 4^5 * \gamma_3 + 4^4 \gamma_2 + 4^3 \gamma_1 + 4^2 * \alpha + 4^1 * \beta + \lambda] + 1 = \dots + \\ &4^6(\gamma_3 - \gamma_4) + 4^5(\gamma_2 - \gamma_3) + 4^4(\gamma_1 - \gamma_2) + 4^3(\alpha - \gamma_1) + 4^2(\beta - \alpha) + 4^1(\lambda - \beta) + 1 - \lambda \end{aligned}$$

Proof of rule 2:

When we have two different numbers that are similar in base 4, such as $n = (... \gamma_3 \gamma_2 \gamma_1 ... \alpha \beta \lambda)_4$ and $m = (... v_3 v_2 v_1 ... \alpha \beta \lambda)_4$ that are common in some digits according to lemma 1, we see that they have similar digits in base 4 even when they are converted to $3n+1$. Divisibility by 2 for the last terms in $3n+1$ in two numbers is same, and initial sentences have enough 4 for divisibility by 2. This makes similar initial terms in $co(n)$ for two numbers.

Example (1):

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} 111 = \underbrace{(1233)}_4 \\ \text{common part} \\ 1391 = (1 \underbrace{1233})_4 \\ \text{common part} \end{array} \right.$$

and:

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} co(111) \Rightarrow \frac{1}{3} + \frac{2}{3^2} + \frac{4}{3^3} + \frac{8}{3^4} + \frac{32}{3^5} + \frac{64}{3^6} + \frac{4 * 64}{3^7} + \dots \\ co(1391) \Rightarrow \frac{1}{3} + \frac{2}{3^2} + \frac{4}{3^3} + \frac{8}{3^4} + \frac{32}{3^5} + \frac{64}{3^6} + \frac{16 * 64}{3^7} + \dots \end{array} \right.$$

They are common in six terms. We can consider these two numbers as members of this branch:

$$n = 4 * (4 * (4 * (4g + 1) + 2) + 3) + 3$$

$$\text{if } g = 1 \Rightarrow n = 111$$

$$\text{and if } g = 5 \Rightarrow n = 1391$$

Although the number of common terms do not change, the further we go in branching, the numbers of each branch become more similar in $co(n)$. we divide g_{330} into four new branches :

$$\begin{array}{lll}
 g \Rightarrow 4g & 4 * (4 * 4 * 4g + 3) + 3 & g_{3300} \\
 g \Rightarrow 4g + 1 & 4 * (4 * 4 * (4g + 1) + 3) + 3 & g_{3301} \\
 g \Rightarrow 4g + 2 & 4 * (4 * 4 * (4g + 2) + 3) + 3 & g_{3302} \\
 g \Rightarrow 4g + 3 & 4 * (4 * 4 * (4g + 3) + 3) + 3 & g_{3303}
 \end{array}$$

That $15 \in g_{3300} = \{15, 271, 527, 783, \dots\}$. the further we go until we reach $g_{3300000}$, that numbers of this branch contains all hailstone terms of $co(15)$. These are $coco(15)$:

$$g_{3300000} = \{15, 16399, 32783, 4917, 65551, 81935, \dots\}$$

4. We can make two different tree- diagrams:

4.a. the zi_3 -diagram

In the zi_3 -diagram, according to rule 2, we categorize natural numbers into different branches by modularity of 4. The more we proceed with branching, the more number in branches become similar to their own $co(n)$, so we continue to reach suitable branches, whose numbers have enough common terms in their $co(n)$, then with the help of rule 1, we reduce $zi(n)$ to $zi(k)$ so that $k < n$ in each branch. The path includes horizontal and vertical movements, and the path for each branch in this diagram isn't unique and you can make different diagrams. Numbers in every branch are $co-zi$ of each other according to that diagram. Number of branches in this diagram is finite. We use this diagram to prove zi -existence theorem or theorem A and also collatz conjecture.

4.b. the co -diagram

In the co_3 -diagram according to rule number 2, we categorize natural numbers into different branches by modularity of 4, but we don't use rule 1. The more we proceed with branching, the more numbers of branches become similar in base-4 and $co(n)$, so we continue branching until we reach the appropriate branches, whose numbers take same steps to reduce $co(n)$ to $co(k)$ so that $k < n$. The number of branches in this diagram is infinite that we called them primary branches. The path in this diagram only has horizontal movement and it is unique for each branch.

5. the Zi_3 -diagram and description

we have described two rules:

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l}
 \text{rule 1. obtaining } zi(n) \text{ from } zi\left(\frac{n-1}{2}\right). \\
 \text{rule 2. The more two natural numbers have similarity in base - 4, the more they have} \\
 \text{similarity in } co(n), \text{ or the more common terms in their } co(n).
 \end{array} \right.$$

Now, in the zi -diagram, we use these two rules to categorize numbers into different branches according to modularity of 4. We continue branching until we reach appropriate branches whose numbers are enough common terms between their $co(n)$, consequently these number have common terms when convert to $\frac{n-1}{2}$ so we can use rule number one to reduce $zi(n)$ to $zi(k)$. This path is not unique. I only use obtaining $zi(n)$ from $zi\left(\frac{n-1}{2}\right)$ as rule number 2.

However, you can make the zi-diagram shorter if you accept 0 and 1 in numerators of $z_i(n)$ and accept all algebraic rules of such series as Rule Number 1.

Here is the first page of branching numbers at the beginning of the zi-diagram below. Aftermath it will continued to reach branches that have a suitable path for reducing $z_i(n)$ to $z_i(k)$ such that $k < n$. The branches are finite in this tree-diagram.

In some branches, when we continue n according to collatz sequence, we reach k , where $k < n$. for example $g_1, g_{3300}, g_{3302}, g_{32101211}, \dots$

In some branches, we can obtain $z_i(n)$ from $z_i(\frac{n-1}{2})$ directly, such as: $g_{3321}, g_{3323}, g_{3301}, \dots$

But in some branches, we need to choose a complicated path, include horizontal and vertical movements to reach the right number such as k , so that $\frac{k-1}{2}$ has two conditions:

- a. We should be able to obtain $z_i(k)$ from $z_i(\frac{k-1}{2})$ with algebraic changes in the initial terms of $z_i(\frac{k-1}{2})$.

These number 10 common terms in their co(n)

Path:

$$zi(n) \Rightarrow \frac{1}{3} + \frac{2}{3^2} + \frac{4}{3^3} + \frac{16}{3^4} + \frac{64}{3^4} zi(k) \quad (1)$$

$$\swarrow zi(k_1) \quad k_1 = \frac{k-1}{2}$$

$$zi(k_1) \Rightarrow \frac{1}{3} + \frac{2}{3^2} + \frac{4}{3^3} + \frac{8}{3^4} + \frac{8 * 16}{3^5} + \frac{2^\alpha * 8 * 16 zi(k_2)}{3^5} \quad k_2 < n$$

Now we obtain zi(k) from zi(k₁) algebraically, then substitute it in (1), and we obtain zi(n).

$$zi(k_1) \Rightarrow \frac{1}{3} + \frac{2}{3^2} + \frac{4}{3^3} + \frac{8}{3^4} + \frac{8 * 16}{3^5} + \frac{2^\alpha * 8 * 16 zi(k_2)}{3^5}$$

2 0 1

Because: $4+3*2+9*1=1+3*0+9*2$

$$2 * \tilde{zi}(k_1) \Rightarrow 2 * k_1 + \frac{4}{3} + \frac{0}{3^2} + \frac{2}{3^3} + \frac{16}{3^4} + \frac{16 * 16}{3^5} + \frac{16 * 16 * 2^\alpha}{3^5} zi(k_2)$$

$$2 * \tilde{zi}(k_1) \Rightarrow \underbrace{2 * k_1 + 1}_k + \frac{1}{3} + \frac{0}{3^2} + \frac{2}{3^3} + \frac{16}{3^4} + \frac{16 * 16}{3^5} + \frac{16 * 16 * 2^\alpha}{3^5} zi(k_2)$$

$$2 * \tilde{zi}(k_1) \Rightarrow \tilde{zi}(k) \Rightarrow k + \frac{1}{3} + \frac{0}{3^2} + \frac{2}{3^3} + \frac{16}{3^4} + \frac{16 * 16}{3^5} + \frac{16 * 16 * 2^\alpha}{3^5} zi(k_2)$$

$$(1) \Rightarrow zi(n) \Rightarrow \frac{1}{3} + \frac{2}{3^2} + \frac{4}{3^3} + \frac{16}{3^4} + \frac{64}{3^4} * \left[\frac{1}{3} + \frac{0}{3^2} + \frac{2}{3^3} + \frac{16}{3^4} + \frac{16 * 16}{3^5} + \frac{16 * 16 * 2^\alpha}{3^5} zi(k_2) \right]$$

$$zi(n) \Rightarrow \frac{1}{3} + \frac{2}{3^2} + \frac{4}{3^3} + \frac{16}{3^4} + \frac{64}{3^5} + \frac{0}{3^6} + \frac{128}{3^7} + \frac{64 * 16}{3^8} + \frac{64 * 16 * 16}{3^9} + \frac{64 * 16 * 16 * 2^\alpha}{3^9} zi(k_2)$$

$$zi(n) \Rightarrow \frac{1}{3} + \frac{2}{3^2} + \frac{4}{3^3} + \frac{16}{3^4} + \frac{64}{3^5} + \frac{0}{3^6} + \frac{128}{3^7} + \frac{64 * 16}{3^8} + \frac{64 * 16 * 16}{3^9} + \frac{64 * 256 * 2^\alpha}{3^9} zi(k_2)$$

$$zi(n) \Rightarrow \frac{1}{3} + \frac{2}{3^2} + \frac{4}{3^3} + \frac{16}{3^4} + \frac{64}{3^5} + \frac{32}{3^6} + \frac{32}{3^7} + \frac{64 * 16}{3^8} + \frac{64 * 16 * 16}{3^9} + \frac{64 * 256 * 2^\alpha}{3^9} zi(k_2)$$

If $n=24903 \Rightarrow \alpha=5 \quad k_2=935$; $n=90439 \Rightarrow \alpha=2 \quad k_2=27163$ and so on.

The path of this branch according to jnzi(n):

$$\begin{array}{l} \text{horizontal move} \\ \text{Jnzi}(n) \Rightarrow \overbrace{2 \quad 2 \quad 4 \quad 4} \\ \text{vertical move} \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \swarrow \\ \searrow \end{array} \right. 2 \quad 2 \quad 2 \quad 16 \quad 2^\alpha zi(k_2) \end{array}$$

Example 2.

We consider the branch $g_{310100131}$

$$g_{310100131} = \{118855, 380999, 643143, 905287, \dots\}$$

path:

$$\tilde{z}i(n) \Rightarrow n + \frac{1}{3} + \frac{2}{3^2} + \frac{4}{3^3} + \frac{16}{3^4} + \frac{64}{3^4} + \frac{128}{3^5} + \frac{4 * 128}{3^5} zi(k) \quad (1)$$

$$\tilde{z}i(k_2) \Rightarrow k_2 + \frac{1}{3} + \frac{2}{3^2} + \frac{32}{3^3} + \frac{64}{3^4} + \frac{2^\alpha * 64 zi(k_3)}{3^4}$$

We first obtain $zi(k_1)$ from $zi(k_2)$, then obtain $zi(k)$ from $zi(k_1)$, and finally we put $zi(k)$ in equation 1, and we obtain $zi(n)$.

$$\tilde{z}i(k_2) \Rightarrow k_2 + \frac{1}{3} + \frac{2}{3^2} + \frac{32}{3^3} + \frac{64}{3^4} + \frac{2^\alpha * 64 zi(k_3)}{3^4}$$

$\begin{matrix} 2 & 16 & 1 & 4 \end{matrix}$

Because: $64 + 3 * 32 + 9 * 2 + 27 * 1 = 4 + 3 * 1 + 9 * 16 + 27 * 2$

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{z}i(k_2) &\Rightarrow k_2 + \frac{2}{3} + \frac{16}{3^2} + \frac{1}{3^3} + \frac{4}{3^4} + \frac{2^\alpha * 64 zi(k_3)}{3^4} \\ 2 * \tilde{z}i(k_2) &\Rightarrow zi(k_1) \Rightarrow \underbrace{2 * k_2 + 1}_{k_1} + \frac{1}{3} + \frac{32}{3^2} + \frac{2}{3^3} + \frac{8}{3^4} + \frac{2^\alpha * 128 zi(k_3)}{3^4} \end{aligned}$$

So:

$$zi(k_1) \Rightarrow k_1 + \frac{1}{3} + \frac{32}{3^2} + \frac{2}{3^3} + \frac{8}{3^4} + \frac{2^\alpha * 128 zi(k_3)}{3^4}$$

$\begin{matrix} 2 & 16 & 1 & 128 \end{matrix}$

Because: $8 + 3 * 2 + 9 * 32 + 27 * 1 = 128 + 3 * 1 + 9 * 16 + 27 * 2$

$$2 * \tilde{z}_i(k_1) \Rightarrow z_i(k) \Rightarrow \frac{2 * k_1 + 1}{k} + \frac{1}{3} + \frac{32}{3^2} + \frac{2}{3^3} + \frac{256}{3^4} + \frac{2^\alpha * 256z_i(k_3)}{3^4}$$

$$\tilde{z}_i(k) \Rightarrow k + \frac{1}{3} + \frac{32}{3^2} + \frac{2}{3^3} + \frac{256}{3^4} + \frac{2^\alpha * 256z_i(k_3)}{3^4}$$

$$(1) \Rightarrow \tilde{z}_i(n) \Rightarrow n + \frac{1}{3} + \frac{2}{3^2} + \frac{4}{3^3} + \frac{16}{3^4} + \frac{64}{3^4} + \frac{128}{3^5} + \frac{4 * 128}{3^5} * \left[\frac{1}{3} + \frac{32}{3^2} + \frac{2}{3^3} + \frac{256}{3^4} + \frac{2^\alpha * 256z_i(k_3)}{3^4} \right]$$

$$\tilde{z}_i(n) \Rightarrow n + \frac{1}{3} + \frac{2}{3^2} + \frac{4}{3^3} + \frac{16}{3^4} + \frac{64}{3^4} + \frac{128}{3^5} + \frac{4 * 128}{3^6} + \frac{4 * 128 * 32}{3^7} + \frac{8 * 128}{3^8} + \frac{4 * 128 * 256}{3^9} + \frac{2^\alpha * 4 * 128 * 256z_i(k_3)}{3^9}$$

If n=118855 ⇒ α=2 k₃=13387

N=380999 ⇒ α=1 k₃= 85823 and so on.

Path according to jnzi(n):

Jnzi(n) ⇒ 2 2 4 4 2 4zi(k)

zi(k₁)

zi(k₂) ⇒ 2 16 2 2^α × zi(k₃)

Example3.

the branch g₃₁₀₁₁₀₂₀₃

$$g_{310110203} = \{205127, 467271, 729415, 991559, \dots\}$$

Path:

Jnzi(n) ⇒ 2 2 4 4zi(k)

zi(k₁)

zi(k₂)

zi(k₃)

jnzi(k₃) ⇒ 2 16 2 2zi(k₄)

nzi(k₃) ⇒ 1+2+32+64+128+2^α × 128zi(k₄)

2 16 2 1

$$(i) \Rightarrow 1+32+4+2+256+2^\alpha \times 256 z_i(k_4) \Leftrightarrow z_i(k_2)$$

$$2 \quad 0 \quad 1 \quad 16 \quad 16 \times 64$$

$$(ii) \Rightarrow 1+0+2+32+2048+2^\alpha \times 512 z_i(k_4) \Leftrightarrow z_i(k_1)$$

$$2 \quad 0 \quad 1 \quad 8$$

$$(iii) \Rightarrow 1+0+2+16+2 \times 2048+2^\alpha \times 2 \times 512 z_i(k_4) \Leftrightarrow z_i(k)$$

$$(1) \Rightarrow \tilde{z}_i(n) \Rightarrow n + \frac{1}{3} + \frac{2}{3^2} + \frac{4}{3^3} + \frac{16}{3^4} + \frac{64}{3^4} * \left[\frac{1}{3} + \frac{0}{3^2} + \frac{2}{3^3} + \frac{16}{3^4} + \frac{2 * 2048}{3^5} + \frac{2^\alpha * 2 * 512}{3^5} z_i(k_4) \right]$$

$$\tilde{z}_i(n) \Rightarrow n + \frac{1}{3} + \frac{2}{3^2} + \frac{4}{3^3} + \frac{16}{3^4} + \frac{64}{3^5} + \frac{32}{3^6} + \frac{32}{3^7} + \frac{64 * 16}{3^8} + \frac{128 * 2048}{3^9} + \frac{2^\alpha * 128 * 512}{3^9} z_i(k_4)$$

$$\text{If } n=205127 \Rightarrow \alpha=2 \quad k_4=15403$$

$$N=467271 \Rightarrow \alpha=3 \quad k_4=17543 \text{ and so on.}$$

6. Theorem(A)

Zi₃-existence-theorem, which is a weak form of collatz theorem:

There is $z_i(n)$ for every natural number; in other words, all natural numbers can be converted into base $-\frac{1}{3}$.

Proof:

In the z_i -diagram, we have categorized numbers into different branches according to modularity of 4, and we continue branching until we reach branches whose numbers are enough similar in base-4, then we have reduced $z_i(n)$ to $z_i(k)$ by a path so that $k < n$ in each branch. With the z_i -diagram, we can obtain $z_i(n)$ for every n . First, we should determine n belongs to which branch of diagram, and in that branch, we reduce $z_i(n)$ to $z_i(k)$ so that $k < n$. Now k belongs to another branch in the z_i -diagram, and we can reduce k to a smaller number. By continuing this process again and again, we reach 1, and we find $z_i(n)$ for all the natural numbers. This proves theorem A.

For example, suppose $n=24903$

$$n \in \mathcal{G}_{31011021}$$

According to the zi_3 -diagram in this branch we have:

$$zi(24903) \Rightarrow \frac{1}{3} + \frac{2}{3^2} + \frac{4}{3^3} + \frac{16}{3^4} + \frac{64}{3^5} + \frac{32}{3^6} + \frac{32}{3^7} + \frac{64 * 16}{3^8} + \frac{64 * 16 * 16}{3^9} + \frac{64 * 256 * 2^5}{3^9} zi(935) \quad (1)$$

Now $935 = (32213)_4$ this belong to g_{312} in the zi_3 -diagram, and we have:

$$zi(935) \Rightarrow \frac{1}{3} + \frac{8}{3^2} + \frac{2}{3^3} + \frac{2^1 * 32}{3^3} zi(395) \quad (2)$$

$n=395 \in g_{32021}$ according to the zi_3 -diagram for g_{320} , we have:

$$zi(395) \Rightarrow \frac{1}{3} + \frac{2}{3^2} + \frac{8}{3^3} + \frac{64}{3^3} zi(167) \quad (3)$$

$n=167 \in g_{3122}$ according to branch g_{312} in the zi_3 -diagram we have:

$$zi(167) \Rightarrow \frac{1}{3} + \frac{8}{3^2} + \frac{2}{3^3} + \frac{2^1 * 32}{3^3} zi(71) \quad (4)$$

$n=71 \in g_{3101}$ in the zi_3 -diagram belongs to $g_{31010000}$

$$nzi(71) \Rightarrow 1 + 2 + 4 + 16 + 64 + 128 + 4 * 128 + 32 * 128 + 8 * 128 + 2^3 * 4 * 128 * 32zi(11) \quad (5)$$

$n=11 \in g_{320}$

$$nzi(11) \Rightarrow 1 + 2 + 8 + 2^3 * 8zi(5) \quad (6)$$

$n=5 \in g_1$

$$nzi(5) \Rightarrow 1 + 16zi(1) \quad (7)$$

When we replace (7) by (6), then (6) by (5), and so on, we obtain $zi(24903)$:

$$zi(24903) \Rightarrow \frac{1}{3} + \frac{2}{3^2} + \frac{4}{3^3} + \frac{16}{3^4} + \frac{64}{3^5} + \frac{32}{3^6} + \frac{32}{3^7} + \frac{64 * 16}{3^8} + \frac{64 * 16 * 16}{3^9} + \frac{64 * 256 * 2^5}{3^9} + \frac{2^{22}}{3^{10}} + \frac{2^{20}}{3^{11}} + \frac{2^{25}}{3^{12}} + \frac{2^{26}}{3^{13}} + \frac{2^{28}}{3^{14}} + \frac{2^{31}}{3^{15}} + \frac{2^{34}}{3^{16}} + \frac{2^{32}}{3^{17}} + \frac{2^{37}}{3^{18}} + \frac{2^{38}}{3^{19}} + \frac{2^{39}}{3^{20}} + \frac{2^{41}}{3^{21}} + \frac{2^{43}}{3^{22}} + \frac{2^{44}}{3^{23}} + \frac{2^{46}}{3^{24}} + \frac{2^{49}}{3^{25}} + \frac{2^{47}}{3^{26}} + \frac{2^{54}}{3^{27}} + \frac{2^{55}}{3^{28}} + \frac{2^{57}}{3^{29}} + \frac{2^{60}}{3^{30}} + \frac{2^{64}}{3^{30}} = \frac{2^{64}}{3^{30}}$$

7. primary branches and description of co-diagram

As in the zi -diagram, according to rule number 2, we categorize numbers in different branches by modularity of 4, but here we don't use rule number 1, and we branching out these until we reach the primary branches. A primary branch (b_p) is a branch whose all of its numbers take the same steps in collatz sequence to reach a smaller number than themselves. In other words, they have the same $T_{sohco}(n)$. The number of b_p 's in the co-diagram are infinite. The first b_p is g_1 .

for example: $g_{3121001}$ is a b_p .

$$g_{3121001} = \{4199, 20583, 36967, 53351, \dots\}$$

With $T_{\text{SOHCO}(N)} = 8$ and with different $T_{\text{SCO}(N)}$

$$4199 + \frac{1}{3} + \frac{2}{3^2} + \frac{4}{3^3} + \frac{16}{3^4} + \frac{32}{3^5} + \frac{64}{3^6} + \frac{128}{3^7} + \frac{512}{3^8} = \frac{64 * 512}{3^8} * (841)$$

$$20583 + \frac{1}{3} + \frac{2}{3^2} + \frac{4}{3^3} + \frac{16}{3^4} + \frac{32}{3^5} + \frac{64}{3^6} + \frac{128}{3^7} + \frac{512}{3^8} = \frac{32 * 512}{3^8} * (8243)$$

.
.

.

Some b_p :

$g_1, g_{300}, g_{301}, g_{302}, g_{303}, g_{3100}, g_{3102}, g_{3103}, g_{313}, g_{311}, g_{3120}, g_{3121}, g_{312200000000}$

$g_{3121001}, g_{312100001000}, \dots, g_{3121000010010000100000},$ and so on

we can name these branches by the first number of these branches, such as:

$g_1 \Rightarrow g_1$ and $g_{300} \Rightarrow g_3; g_{301} \Rightarrow g_{19}; \dots$

A question:

How many primary branches are there whose first number is smaller than n ?

8. Converting z_i 's of n to each other

According to the theorem (A), for every n , we have:

$$\tilde{z}_i(n) \Rightarrow n + \frac{1}{3} + \frac{2^{\alpha_1}}{3^2} + \frac{2^{\alpha_2}}{3^3} + \dots \dots \dots \frac{2^{\alpha_i}}{3^i} = \frac{2^\alpha}{3^i}$$

We close $z_i(n)$, in the second term:

$$\tilde{z}_i(n) \Rightarrow n + \frac{1}{3} + \frac{2^{\alpha_1}}{3^2} z_i(k)$$

Therefore:

$$\tilde{z}_i(n) \Rightarrow n + \frac{1}{3} + \frac{2^{\alpha_1} * 2^r}{3^2} \frac{z_i(k)}{2^r} = n + \frac{1}{3} + \frac{2^{\alpha_1+r}}{3^2} z_i\left(\frac{k}{2^r}\right)$$

That $zi(q) \in zi\text{-diagram}$.

Actually, you can use the branches in the $zi\text{-diagram}$ as elements to make any zi , even $co(n)$, from them.

According to theorem A, we know $all\ zi(n) \in zi\text{-diagram} \longrightarrow zi(1)$, therefore:

$$co(n) = n + \frac{1}{3} + \sum_t^i \left[\frac{2^{\alpha_i}}{3^{\gamma_t}} \right] + \frac{2^\alpha}{3^{\gamma_t+1}} zi(q) \longrightarrow zi(1)$$

If $co(n)$ don't end with $co(1)$ then there is a $zi(m)$ in the $zi\text{-diagram}$ don't end with 1 and theorem(A) must be false.

10. Original theorem of arithmetic rule (rule number2) and generalization

About collatz sequence we have:

$$f(n) = \begin{cases} \frac{n}{2} & n \equiv 2 \\ 3k + 1 & n \not\equiv 2 \end{cases}$$

It is a sequence with the expression $3k+1$ and divisors 2^α ; $\alpha \geq 1$ that wondrous numbers $\in \mathbb{N}$.

In rule 2, we have seen The more two numbers are similar in base 4, the more they have similar terms in their $co(n)$. This is true also for base 2 and other powers of 2 such as 8, 16, etc . So we can branch numbers according to modularity of 2 in the $zi\text{-diagram}$ instead of 4 or other powers of 2 and make different $zi_3\text{-diagrams}$.

About $base - \frac{1}{5}$ we have a sequence with the expression $5k+1$ and divisors 2^α and 3^β .

The more two numbers are similar in base 6, the more they have similar terms in their $co_5(n)$, so we can arrange a $zi_5\text{-diagram}$ according to modularity 6 or 36,etc., and if we could reduce any branch of this diagram with the help of the algebraic rules of $co_5(n)$, then we can say each number can be written to $base - \frac{1}{5}$, and consequently we can prove generalize collatz for $5k+1$.

It is done in the same way for other base.

original Theorem: In a sequence

$$f(n) = \begin{cases} an + k & n \not\equiv p_1, p_2, p_3, \dots \\ \frac{n}{p_1} & n \equiv p_1 \\ \frac{n}{p_2} & n \equiv p_2 \\ \vdots & \vdots \end{cases}$$

with the expression $ax+k$ and divisors $F^m = p_1^m \cdot p_2^m \dots$

The more two numbers are similar in base F, the more they have similar terms in their sequence. Then we can arrange a $zi_a\text{-diagram}$ according to modularity of F or F^2 , etc. If we could reduce every

branch of this diagram to a number smaller than n. This shows the only loops happening here are those among initial numbers of N.

One result of above is the answer of this equation in the base f:

$$x + k = F^n$$

$$\text{If } k = \underbrace{(\dots \alpha \beta \gamma \lambda)}_{m \text{ digits}}_F \quad n \geq m$$

Answer of this equation in the base of F is:

$$x = \dots + (f-1)f^5 + (f-1)f^4 + \dots + (f-\alpha-1)f^3 + (f-\beta-1)f^2 + (f-\gamma-1)f + (f-\lambda)$$

$$= g(f)_{[(f-1)(f-1)\dots(f-\alpha-1)(f-\beta-1)(f-\gamma-1)(f-\lambda)]} = g(f)_{[(f-1)\dots(f-\alpha-1)(f-\beta-1)(f-\gamma-1)(f-\lambda)]}$$

Here, f is the base.

For example: $x+8=5^n$

$$8 = (13)_5$$

$$X = g(5)_{[(5-1)(5-1-1)(5-3)]} = \begin{cases} (5-1-1)5 + (5-3) = 17 \\ (5-1)5^2 + (5-1-1)5 + (5-3) = 117 \\ 4 * 5^3 + 4 * 5^2 + 3 * 5 + 2 = 617 \\ \vdots \\ \vdots \\ \vdots \end{cases}$$

So: $X = g(5)_{[(5-1)(5-2)(5-3)]}$

For equation: $ax+k=F^n$

if $k = (\dots \alpha \beta \gamma \lambda)_F$ and $a = (ijrq)_F$

Answer obtain from this equation:

$$g(F) \dots ijrq * x = g(F)_{[(f-1)\dots(f-\alpha-1)(f-\beta-1)(f-\gamma-1)(f-\lambda)]}$$

11. Conclusion

In this paper, we proved collatz conjecture only with two simple rules. We actually used a relationship between $co(n)$ and modularity of 4.

With two rules, we make the zi_3 -diagram that it shows all natural numbers can be converted into $base - \frac{1}{3}$. In part 2, we will represent the zi_3 -diagram. This led to a proof of collatz conjecture. This method can be used for:

1. other bases such as: $1/5, 1/7, \dots$
2. other forms of collatz problem's generalizations. We can even, arrange a similar diagram for negative integer.

You can write the zi_5 -diagram which could be easier than zi_3 -diagram, or the zi -diagrams for other bases: $zi_7, zi_{11}, \dots$

But writing the zi_n -diagram is time-consuming.

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